

PERFORMANCE CHARACTERISTICS OF KEVLAR-49 TENSION MEMBERS*

George A. Wilkins
Naval Undersea Center
P. O. Box 997
Kailua, Hawaii 96734

Test data are reported for multiple filaments of DuPont's KEVLAR-49, joined in urethane and epoxy matrices in a structure equivalent to the steel wires used in conventional cables. Ultimate tensile strength is greater than 250,000 psi, with a tensile modulus of more than 12,000,000 psi and a linear stress/strain curve. Flexure lifetime is more than 2,000,000 cycles at 20% of ultimate stress and a sheave-to-member diameter ratio of 50/1. (Under the same conditions, improved plow steel wires fail after about 1000 cycles.) Specific gravity is 1.34, which gives a strength/weight advantage over improved plow steel of about 6.5 in air and 24 in seawater. The members are unaffected by high pressures, but are degraded in strength and modulus by 20-month exposure to weather and coastal seawater. Creep-to-failure lifetimes (at 50% of ultimate stress) are essentially infinite for unflawed members.

On the negative side, these members have a high coefficient of variation ($\approx 4\%$) in both strength and modulus, and a near-zero correlation between these two parameters. They show no evidence of an elastic limit near ultimate tensile stress. These factors make it difficult or impossible to build a cable which is stress- or torque balanced, and degrade the strength of such a cable from the value predicted from average member properties.

Performance data are presented for three types of KEVLAR-49 tension members and two prototype KEVLAR-49 cables. A cable model is described which more accurately predicts breaking strength. Cable termination techniques are also discussed.

*Supported by the Chief of Naval Material as part of the Deep Ocean Technology (DOT) Project.

Introduction

As cable-tethered operations are extended to greater ocean depths, the problem of self-weight becomes extremely serious with conventional electromechanical cables. The ratio of strength to weight (i.e., safety factor) shrinks to the point that massive and expensive motion-compensating systems may be required to prevent dynamic tension surges from parting the cable. Payload capacity is reduced. The weight of the cable and its handling system create logistic problems if they are to be transported, or transferred from one ship to another. Ships of increased displacement may even be needed to carry the greater weight of the cable system. These deep ocean engineering problems have close analogies in other fields; e.g., cable hoists in mine shafts, power transmission lines, and tether lines for moored communications balloons.

In conventional cables, the fault lies primarily with the density of the steel loadbearing members. As the cross-sectional area of steel is increased to give more strength, the weight of the cable also increases. The ratio of strength to weight remains almost constant, while the cable becomes heavier, stiffer, and more difficult to handle and deploy. If the problem is to be solved, design alternatives include the following.

- Add a second, lightweight rope to carry the weight of a simple electrical cable. This complicates the handling system, and increases the magnitude and variance of cable drag. Typical synthetic ropes have such a low elastic modulus that the electrical cable is likely to be overstressed.
- Attach a buoyancy module to the cable at a mid-depth point, typically 5,000 to 10,000 feet. This adds a failure-prone, expensive element. It also increases cable drag, as well as the complexity of launch and recovery operations.
- Decrease the weight of all inert (i.e., nonloadbearing) elements in the cable. This gives, at best, only a minor increment of improvement. For most steel-armored electrical cables, such elements represent less than 20% of the cable's in-water weight.
- Increase the tensile strength of the loadbearing section; e.g., use steel of 300,000 psi tensile strength rather than 250,000 psi. Again, this is a small increment of improvement compared to the magnitude of the problem. It also carries penalties of greater corrosion susceptibility and reduced lifetime under loaded flexure.
- Decrease the density of the loadbearing section, with as little sacrifice as possible in its tensile strength and tensile modulus.

The last of these alternatives--an approach using DuPont's KEVLAR-49 (1) in a composite tension member--was chosen by the Naval Undersea Center during the development of a cable-controlled system to work on the seafloor at a depth of 20,000 feet. Figure 1 gives an insight to the reasons for this choice. Supporting data are shown in Table I.

Table I. Properties of Cables and Tension Members

As Plotted in Figure 1	Specific Gravity or In-Seawater Weight*	Strength or Tensile Strength
a) KEVLAR-49 member	1.34	250,000 psi
b) S-Glass member (2)	2.08	340,000 psi
c) 2J69RC coax (KEVLAR-49)	0.070 lb/ft	37,800 lb
d) Prototype coax (KEVLAR-49)	0.316 lb/ft	97,800 lb
e) Titanium wire	4.43	138,000 psi
f) Steel wire	7.8	225,000 psi
g) 2J69RC coax (steel) (3)	0.562 lb/ft	34,000 lb
h) Hard-drawn copper wire	8.89	60,000 psi

* For a seawater specific gravity of 1.025

The three metallic tension members are evaluated as simple support wires. Even without allowance for the weight of electrical components or payload, all fail the standard ocean engineering criterion of a safety factor of 5 at 20,000 feet. (Copper would break of its own weight at a depth of 17,600 feet.)

Plot g represents U.S. Steel's 2J69RC armored coax, an undersea cable in extensive use for deep ocean tows. Without any payload, it offered a safety factor of barely 3 at 20,000 feet, and had unacceptably high air- and deployed weights.

In composite form, KEVLAR-49 and S-Glass had a very desirable combination of high tensile strength and low density. Although its composite tensile strength was lower, KEVLAR-49 projected improved performance in ocean applications because its specific gravity was much closer to that of seawater. For that reason, and because of the high and undesirable rigidity of S-Glass members, KEVLAR-49 was chosen for the loadbearing section in the prototype cable for the 20,000-foot work system (Plot d).

The expected gain in strength-to-weight ratio is illustrated by Plot c in Figure 1. Here, the 2J69RC cable is modified by direct substitution of KEVLAR-49 composite tension members for steel, with no change in number or diameter of members. The improvement in safety factor is nearly 9/1; from 3.03 to 26.8 at a depth of 20,000 feet. The improvement would have been much greater, except that the in-water weight of the nonloadbearing

section remained constant while the weight in water of the armor was reduced by a factor of more than 20.

Evaluation of KEVLAR-49 Tension Members

Three types of tension members, each from a different company, have been tested for suitability as the loadbearing element in electromechanical cables. All were constructed from multiple 1420-Denier yarns of KEVLAR-49. This yarn is advertised as containing 1000 filaments, each of diameter 0.00047" (1), but the data reported here will be based on observed diameters which average 0.00046". The properties of KEVLAR-49 are well documented (1,4,5, 6,7).

Wherever possible, these tension members have been tested under identical conditions. Prototype cables, however, have been made only with members from U.S. Polymeric. Extensive cable testing and analyses, using tension members from Philadelphia Resins, have been done by the Naval Underwater Systems Center (8,9).

U.S. Polymeric, Santa Ana, California. Most of the effort reported here has focused on these tension members, and preliminary data have already been published (7). KEVLAR-49 yarns are initially dipcoated ("prepregged") in an ether-based, thermoplastic, urethane resin (10). The yarns are then passed through an oven, which remelts the resin, and twisted into a helix. Nominal helix lay length is 1.0" for all filaments. The twisting and melting combine to squeeze residual vapor and air voids out of the helix. Finally, the member is pulled through a sizing die and quickly cooled below the resin softening temperature. The result is a composite system with low void content (< 0.5%) and a thin coating of resin around each filament. Member specific gravity, by helium/air displacement, is 1.34 ± 0.01 . Members have been fabricated in three diameters, as shown in Table II.

Table II. U.S. Polymeric Tension Members

Member Diameter	Number of Yarns	Number of Filaments	Relative Filament Cross Section
0.048"	7	7,000	0.64
0.073"	18	18,000	0.71
0.097"	30	30,000	0.67

Philadelphia Resins, Montgomeryville, Pennsylvania. These tension members are built from seven composite strands in a 1-6 helix construction (6). Each strand contains 3 straight-lay yarns of KEVLAR-49 in a matrix described as a "low modulus, polyether-based polyurethane" (11). The helix length is nominally 1.0", and the member diameter is about 0.088" at 5% of ultimate stress. (The

helix is quite loose and "soft".) Specific gravity is reported as 1.21 (6) which, considering the density of the components, means that the strands should contain about 15% voids. Data reported here are from samples designated by the company as PS-49-C.08.

Air Logistics, Pasadena, California. These members are produced as a straight-lay composite of 12 KEVLAR-49 yarns in a resin matrix described as a "polyamide modified, amine cured epoxy" (12). The filament cross-sectional fraction is 0.52 and average member diameter is 0.070". The specific gravity is reported as 1.22 (12), which again appears to be too low unless the void content is about 14%.

Tensile Strength and Tensile Modulus

Samples from these members were pulled to break on an Instron universal test machine, and measurements made of breaking load and elongation under load. The results are given in Table III. Test conditions included: 10" sample gauge length, 1" extensometer gauge length, and a strain rate of 1 in/min. All samples were tab-terminated, and tests were considered valid only if the break was clearly not influenced by the tab.

Initially, extensometer measurements were continued to member rupture to verify the shape of the stress/strain curve. Typical curves are shown in Figure 2, with a plot for 225,000 psi steel for comparison. None of the three types of KEVLAR-49 tension members showed any evidence of a yield limit. Failure tended to be sudden--almost explosive--with considerable risk of damage to the extensometer. Because of this, the data summarized in Table III were obtained with the extensometer removed after the load passed 70% of the expected value at break. The stress/strain curve was then extrapolated to the measured breaking load to determine elongation at break.

This subterfuge should introduce less than 0.5% variation in the modulus values shown in Table III for the U.S. Polymeric and Air Logistics members. Their stress/strain curves were straight-edge linear at all loads. Members from Philadelphia Resins, however, showed definite concavity at less than 50% of ultimate stress. For these stranded members, extrapolation of the measured stress/strain curve may have introduced as much as 3% variation into the reported values of tensile modulus.

For all members, tensile modulus is calculated as the ratio of tensile strength to relative elongation at break. This is a precise and accurate statement for the Air Logistics and U.S. Polymeric members. Because of the stress/strain concavity noted earlier, it is only an effective value for the Philadelphia Resins members.

It should be noted that the U.S. Polymeric members were taken from both ends of five 26,000-foot production runs intended for use in a deep-ocean support cable. Samples of the other two members were taken from single lengths supplied by their manufacturers.

Coefficients of Variation. For all members, the coefficients of variation in tensile strength closely match the value observed for single, epoxy-dipped yarns of 1420-Denier KEVLAR-49. None of the assembly techniques appear to add additional strength variance. The same is true for tensile modulus for the members from U.S. Polymeric, while those from Air Logistics appear to have much less modulus variation than has been observed with single yarn.

The high modulus coefficient of variation in the Philadelphia Resins members has already been partially explained. The looseness of the stranded construction, and the noncircular cross sections of the component strands, may be sufficient to explain the remainder of the excess variability.

Strength/Modulus Correlation. Scala (13) has discussed the impact of member strength variations in reducing the achievable breaking load for KEVLAR-49 cables. The correlation between modulus and strength is also important, since the nonyielding KEVLAR-49 tension members cannot "forgive" near-ultimate stresses.

- Ideally, such members would show zero variation in strength and modulus. Under uniform elongation, all members in a cable would then carry equal loads and would break at the same stress.
- Practically, the penalty inflicted by strength variations would be small if the correlation between modulus and strength for the tension members were +1. The member with low tensile strength would have a correspondingly low value of tensile modulus. In carrying less than its share of the cable load, it would still break at the same relative elongation as all other members.
- Actually, Table III shows that there is little correlation between these two parameters. Tests of other tension members from U.S. Polymeric (as will be seen later) show that strength/modulus correlation can be negative. This behavior appears to be a basic property of KEVLAR-49 (14).

Distribution Model. Because of the small population of samples tested to date, little effort has been spent to determine which type of distribution best fits the member strength and modulus data. A Chi-squared test of the U.S. Polymeric tensile strength data in Table III, however, shows less than 50% probability of a match with a Gaussian distribution. For these same data,

Pearson's Measure of Skewness [(mean - mode)/standard deviation] has a value of -0.20, which fits with an observed clustering of strength values above the mean and a scattering of lower values.

Elongation Under Static Load

Tension members from both U.S. Polymeric and Philadelphia Resins have been exposed to static loading in a laboratory (air) environment to determine creep behavior. All samples--86 to date-- have been loaded to 50% of ultimate (short term) stress. Member elongation was measured over a 25" span between gauge blocks attached to a linear section of the specimen. The members were terminated with several wraps around a 6"-diameter cylinder.

Figure 3 shows typical behavior of these tension members under static loading. Specimen S-27 has a diameter of 0.097" and more than 10,000 hours of exposure to load. The diameter of S-73 is 0.088", and it has been under load for more than 6400 hours. Many members have failed at lesser exposures, with the most critical time interval being $0 < t < 1000$ hours. These early failures have always occurred at a localized stress point; i.e., at an end termination or at the point of attachment for a gauge block. Surviving samples continue to elongate, but $\Delta L/L$ becomes a logarithmic function of time.

$$\left[\frac{\Delta L}{L} \right]_T = \left[\frac{\Delta L}{L} \right]_t + C \cdot \text{Log}(T/t) \quad (1)$$

As a purely academic exercise, this relationship has been used to calculate the endurance at 50% loading for samples S-27 and S-73. Two critical assumptions were made. First, the member behavior in the initial several thousand hours will continue indefinitely. Second, both members will fail at the same relative elongation observed during short-term loading. Subject to these (perhaps wildly inaccurate) assumptions, the following "lifetimes" are calculated.

Philadelphia Resins (S-73) 3.3×10^{16} years

U.S. Polymeric (S-27) 6.1×10^{35} years

Only two conclusions are intended here. These two types of KEVLAR-49 tension members rapidly stabilize at 50% of ultimate short-term stress. The creep rate after stabilization is small and predictable.

Loaded Flexure

Tests have been made to determine the flexure lifetimes of all three tension members at various stress levels. The test fixture, sketched in Figure 4, allows tension, sheave radius, flexure angle

and flexure rate to be independently varied. It also allows four sections to be tested simultaneously, with "failure" defined as the initial rupture among these sections. A flexure cycle is defined as one complete rotation of driving wheel A, which results in two bends in each test section. Some may wish to double the flexure rates and lifetimes reported here.

Table IV summarizes the flexure experience gained to date. All tests have been run at flexure rates of 2/second, at a flexure angle of $\pm 28^\circ$, over 4"-diameter aluminum sheaves with semicircular grooves to fit the diameter of the test sample. Each leg of the test loop is tensioned to 20%, 30%, 40%, or 50% of the ultimate short-term stress previously measured for the member. Additional samples reported in the table are described below.

- Eighteen yarns of 1420-Denier KEVLAR-49 were twisted to a helix length of 1.0". This uncoated sample was then flexed at the same absolute load used for the 20% test of the U.S. Polymeric composite tension member. Except for the urethane matrix, the two samples were identical.
- An S-Glass tension member from Air Logistics also was tested, and had the same diameter and epoxy matrix as that company's KEVLAR-49 member. The sample contained 24,600 filaments of 0.00035"-diameter S-Glass (0.615 cross-sectional fraction). Mean tensile strength and mean tensile modulus were 327,000 psi and 8,410,000 psi, respectively.
- The final sample was an 0.097"-diameter wire of 225,000 psi galvanized improved plow steel.

The data in Table IV show much more spread than had been expected, and are being interpreted with caution until many more tests can be run. Only two conclusions can be stated with confidence at this time. First, the U.S. Polymeric and Philadelphia Resins tension members show outstanding flexure lifetimes at loads less than or equal to 30% of ultimate. Second, their failure is not due to flexural fatigue of the KEVLAR-49 filaments, but rather to physical abrasion and erosion of the composite material against the walls of the groove.

The helix twist of these two tension members appears to be the key to their long flexure lifetimes. The member length affected by the $\pm 28^\circ$ flexure is 1.95", approximately 2 cycles of the filament helix. This allows the effect of differential flexure radius to be averaged among all of the KEVLAR-49 filaments.

The Air Logistics members, on the other hand, have straight-lay filaments. These can compensate for differential radii in flexure only by some combination of compression of filaments at the bottom of the groove and elongation of those on the opposite side

of the member. For the test parameters already described, this difference in compression/elongation is 3.5%, sensibly greater than the nominal 2.0% ultimate elongation of KEVLAR-49. The S-Glass can absorb high compressive loading when bound in an epoxy matrix, but KEVLAR-49 cannot. It was difficult to bend the KEVLAR-49 members around the 4"-diameter sheave without buckling them. Both members failed via a successive breaking of those filaments which saw the greatest flexure radius.

Environmental Exposure

Tension members (0.097"-diameter) from an early development phase at U.S. Polymeric have been subjected to three types of environmental exposure: high-pressure cycling and soaking in seawater, exposure to sun and rain, and submergence in a biologically active region of Kaneohe Bay, Oahu, Hawaii.

Pressurization. Several members were cycled 100 times to 10,000 psi in seawater. Others were soaked for 24 hours in seawater at that pressure. The members were pulled to break and compared to control samples. No changes were observed in diameter, specific gravity, tensile strength or tensile modulus. Under microscopic examination, the only visual change was a collapse of tiny voids in the thin annulus of resin which formed the outer surface of the members. If this crushing affected specific gravity, the change was less than 0.005 parts in the 1.34 value measured for the controls.

Exposure to Sun and Rain. Samples were exposed for 20 months on a flat surface near Kaneohe Bay and with no protection from sunlight, marine air and tropical rain. Tests run after a 6-month exposure showed a general whitening of the resin surface, an average of 10% decrease in tensile strength, and no change in tensile modulus. After 20 months, much of the outer urethane surface had disappeared, and the member could be untwisted to expose its component yarns. Mean tensile strength had decreased from the control value of 214,000 psi to 116,800 psi, and tensile modulus from 12,300,000 psi to 10,100,000 psi. Apparently, the mechanism for urethane loss was a combination of degradation by ultraviolet radiation and etching of the end product by the impact of water droplets during heavy tropical rains. (See photograph in Figure 5.)

Exposure to Seawater. These samples were placed on a muddy bottom in Kaneohe Bay at a depth of approximately 18 feet. After six months, they were encrusted with a coral-like growth, but showed no deterioration after the growth was broken away. Tensile strength and tensile modulus matched those of the control samples.

After 20 months in seawater, the encrustation had grown to a maximum diameter of about 1" and was heavily populated with tube worms, sponges, crabs, and the spat of various crustacea. Beneath

this mass, most of the outer annulus of resin had disappeared. The only regions in which the filament helix was disrupted were at points where larger barnacles had attached themselves. Here, the members had localized kinks, probably due to the holdfast mechanism used by the bivalve. These regions also showed signs of biological penetration into the filament helix; probably also a part of the attachment mode. Figure 5 shows one of these disruption points.

Average tensile strength for the 20-month samples was 156,000 psi and average tensile modulus was 5,940,000 psi. Large variations in both parameters were noted from sample to sample.

Protection. These tension members have shown no (purely) aging effects. During the exposures described above, short sections which had been wrapped with black tape showed no visible degradation. The members, as well as cables built from them, probably can be given adequate protection against long exposures with a thin jacket of black urethane. The tension members could be given some protection against sunlight if a solar-blocking agent were used in the urethane.

Use of KEVLAR-49 Composites in Cables

Several KEVLAR-strengthened cables have been developed at the Naval Undersea Center, and two will be discussed here. Each has gone through a prototype and testing phase as a prelude to manufacture of the operational cable. Each illustrates important points which should be considered when KEVLAR-49 is chosen as the loadbearing section of a cable.

- The first cable is a multiconductor unit, and is presented to show that choice of KEVLAR-49 is only the first step towards reduction of cable in-water weight (or increase of strength/weight). If the choice of KEVLAR-49 as a substitute for steel in a conventional cable is followed by the choice of other low density component materials, then the cable can be made light enough to float in water without increasing its diameter.
- The second cable is a contrahelically-armored coax, which was designed to furnish physical support, power and communications to a deep-ocean, remotely-controlled work system. It is presented to demonstrate the mechanical performance of a complex KEVLAR-49 cable, as well as the hazards of trying to predict the strength of such cables with conventional analysis techniques.

Lightweight Array Cable

This cable was designed as a high-strength, low-weight, communication link for use in undersea buoyed arrays. Low weight was needed to reduce the cost, size and weight of the deep buoy which would support the cable and keep it from excessive streaming in high currents. A prototype version is shown in Figure 6. The cable is extremely flexible, and can easily bend around a 2.5"-radius circle without overstressing of the conductors or the central loadbearing section. The cable contains 8 conductors as 4 twisted pairs, and the design allows 10 such pairs to be incorporated without increasing cable diameter. The weight in seawater is 0.030 lb/ft, and cable breaking strength is 16,000 pounds.*

The second version of this cable is now being manufactured. It is shown in cross section in Figure 7. The central loadbearing section contains six 0.097"-diameter and twenty 0.048"-diameter KEVLAR-49 composite tension members, contrahelically wrapped around a monofilament core. This section is jacketed in polyethylene. The 20 conductors are copper-clad aluminum (each 7 strands, #20 AWG), insulated with a methylpentene polymer (TPX) (15). The outer jacket is thermoplastic rubber (TPR) (16). All voids are filled with a polyethylene grease (17).

The cable sketched in Figure 7 can be used as a demonstration model to show the reductions of cable weight which result as lightweight components are substituted for conventional materials. Assume that there are no changes of cable dimensions or helix angles. In the baseline design, all tension members are steel, the conductors are copper insulated with Teflon, all voids are filled with silicone paste, and the outer jacket is polyurethane. Such a design corresponds closely to conventional cables in use today. Table V, shown on the next page, shows the effects of replacing each of these materials with substitutes that have a lower density.

KEVLAR-Armored Coaxial Cable

This cable will serve as the support link to an unmanned work system which is to operate at ocean depths to 20,000 feet. The system design faced two overwhelming constraints. First, the system was to be highly portable (air transportable) as a package which included cable, traction winch and boom. Second, it was to be operable in high seas; normal operations in Sea

*Design breaking strength was 27,000 pounds. This mismatch will be discussed in a later section.

Table V. Effects of Material Selection on Cable Weight

Cable Construction	Cable Weight (lb/ft)	
	In Air	In Seawater*
Conventional multiconductor cable, as described above.	0.834	0.483
a) Replace steel tension members with KEVLAR-49 composites.	0.606	0.256
b) Next, replace conductor insulation with TPX.	0.444	0.093
c) Next, replace urethane outer jacket with TPR.	0.423	0.072
d) Next, replace silicone void filler with polyethylene grease.	0.380	0.029
e) Finally, replace copper conductors with aluminum.	0.330	-0.019#

*Seawater specific gravity is 1.025.
#Final cable specific gravity is 0.97.

State Four and normal recovery in Sea State Five. Considered individually, these constraints made the use of steel tension members in the cable improbable. In unison, they made such use impossible. After an exhaustive evaluation of alternatives--subsurface buoys, two-cable designs, fiberglass tension members, etc.--KEVLAR-49 was chosen as the only workable option. Tensile strength was not the primary factor in this choice; in fact, it was a distinct fourth behind the need for low specific gravity, high tensile modulus and long flexure lifetime.

Two prototype models of the coax cable have been built,* each based on slight modifications of an original Navy design. The South Bay cable is shown in Figure 8, while the ITT version has already been reported (18). Each cable contained a central coax, designed to transmit 40 kilowatts at 3000 volts plus high frequency data (12 megahertz at 2.5 dB/1000'). Each was armored with contrahelical wraps of KEVLAR-49 tension members manufactured by U.S. Polymeric. In both cables, the inner helix contained 28 members of 0.073" diameter and the outer helix held 44 members of 0.073" diameter. Overall cable diameter--less the

*By ITT, San Diego, California and Consolidated Products (South Bay), Idyllwild, California.

urethane outer jacket, which was dropped from the final design-- was 1.20 inches. If the tensile strength of the KEVLAR-49 members could be held uniform at 250,000 psi, and if they could be equally stressed, the design breaking load of the cable was 93,000 pounds. With an in-water weight of approximately 0.31 lb/ft, this would have meant a static safety factor of 15.5 for operations at a depth of 20,000 feet.

One design difference between the two cables was originally considered to be minor, but has turned out to be of critical importance. The South Bay cable contained a 4-mil Mylar tape between the two KEVLAR-49 helices. The ITT cable had no such isolation layer.

Cable Construction. Neither ITT nor South Bay encountered any serious problems in cabling the KEVLAR-49 tension members. The members behaved much like steel armor wires except that they could be formed more easily into the new helix configuration. Preforming was not necessary and, when the cable was later cut into sections for testing, the members showed no tendency to snap out of the helix. The KEVLAR-49 members were reported to be extremely "forgiving". In one instance, it was necessary to reverse the cabling machine and remove about 50 feet of outer armor from the cable. The machine was then restarted and the members were recabled without damage.

Cable Termination. It was necessary to develop an effective method for strength termination of the prototype KEVLAR-49 cables. Obviously, a standard zinc-filled socket would not work. Initial attempts to use an epoxy replacement for zinc--a technique which has been relatively successful with steel armor wires--also failed. The bond between the epoxy and the outer surface of the tension members either developed insufficient shear strength or did not adequately transfer shear forces to the inner filaments of the members. The members pulled out of the epoxy, generally leaving an outer annulus of KEVLAR filaments behind.

One approach, which has been quite successful (19,20), depends on complete replacement of the urethane with epoxy. The cable is passed up through a standard socket and openings among the tension members are blocked with zinc chromate tape. Within the socket, each tension member is taken out of the helix in a direction tangent to the last point of contact and is individually tensioned. The urethane in the tension members is thoroughly washed out with repeated applications of solvent (dimethylformamide or DuPont T-E35). A vacuum is formed around the termination to remove all residual solvent. Finally, a low viscosity epoxy (e.g., Reichhold 37-127 resin with 37-620 Epotuff hardener) is syphoned into the socket under vacuum, and the system is allowed to cure overnight at 120°F.

The epoxy socket is shown in Figure 9. Three points in this procedure are critical to success: the filament helices must not be disturbed, the urethane must be completely replaced by epoxy, and the epoxy fill must be thoroughly outgassed.

Cable Test Results. These are well documented (19,20) and only those results which had major impact on the KEVLAR-49 coaxial cable will be given here.*

- Under loaded flexure (20,000 pounds and 50"-diameter sheaves), the South Bay cable broke after 32,240 to 67,700 cycles. In two tests at the design operating load of 10,000 pounds, this cable survived 100,000 flexure cycles. These two samples were then pulled to break on the sheave, and failed at loads comparable to those experienced for unflexed samples. Failure occurred away from the flexure points. The South Bay cable had been built with a 4-mil Mylar tape between the two armor helices.
- The ITT cable (no Mylar tape) failed in flexure at 21,917 cycles with a 10,000-pound load, and at 19,670 and 24,730 cycles under a 20,000-pound load. These failures resulted from erosion of the two armor helices as they abraded against one another.
- The urethane jacket had no influence on flexure performance or survival. The South Bay cable performed equally well when the outer armor helix was allowed to flex in direct contact with the steel groove of the sheave.
- Pull-to-break test results are summarized in Table VI. Each test resulted in early breaks of individual members, followed by a general cascade of breaks at an ultimate load. These initial failures generally occurred at 40% to 45% of design breaking load. No cable was able to withstand more than 60% of design load. This latter value is gaining some notoriety in the cable industry as the "60% barrier" for KEVLAR-49.
- No failures or degradation of electrical performance were observed at any cable load.
- Except for one or two early failures as the technique was being perfected, the epoxy terminations held up well. The best that can be claimed for this approach, however, is 100% reliability at the 60% load level.

*Cable tests were conducted by Battelle Institute, Long Beach Research Facility, Long Beach, California.

- A post mortem examination was made of failed tension members from partially-broken cables. It showed that those members which broke early had severely (as much as 50%) reduced tensile strength, but much less reduction of tensile modulus. These members would break at a much lower relative elongation than those members which were not degraded.

Final Coax Cable Design. Although the results of the cable strength tests were disappointing, the prototype coaxial cable still met all minimum requirements of the 20,000-foot work system. Its air weight was less than 40% that of a steel cable and, even at the degraded strength level, its safety factor when deployed to 20,000 feet would be twice that available with steel. The decision was made to go ahead with manufacture of a 23,000-foot KEVLAR-49 coaxial cable. In parallel, an analysis would be made of the impact of tension member variations on cable strength, and solutions to the problem of member degradation would be sought.

The final cable design is essentially the same as that shown in Figure 8. The urethane outer jacket was removed since, with reasonable care in handling, it had no useful purpose. The braided shield conductor--which had disintegrated within 10,000 cycles of loaded flexure--was replaced with a helix wrap of 46 silver-coated copper wires, electrically joined with inner and outer layers of copper-polyester tape. Two contrahelical wraps of polyester tape were incorporated as an insulation layer between the KEVLAR-49 loadbearing helices.

The cable is now being built at ITT, San Diego. Table VII summarizes its weight characteristics, and compares them with those of an identical design armored with steel wires.

Table VII. KEVLAR-49 Coaxial Cable

Component	Steel		KEVLAR-49	
	In Air	In Seawater	In Air	In Seawater
Electrical Core Weight (lb/ft)	0.518	0.259	0.518	0.259
Armor Weight (lb/ft)	<u>1.374</u>	<u>1.193</u>	<u>0.247</u>	<u>0.056</u>
Total Weight (lb/ft)	1.892	1.452	0.765	0.315

The deployed weight for 20,000-foot depths would be over 29,000 pounds with a steel cable, but only 6,300 pounds with KEVLAR-49. Notice that the electrical core--common to both cable designs--is 82% of the in-water weight of the KEVLAR-49 cable, but only 18% for the steel cable. Much of this nonloadbearing weight was forced on the 20,000-foot system by the need for data bandwidth

and high-power transmission. Still, it is obvious that weight reduction in the tension members has been pushed beyond the point of diminishing returns, and future attempts to reduce in-water weight should be directed at the electrical section of the cable.

Post Mortem Evaluation

Following the cable test series, several samples of the South Bay and ITT prototype coaxial cables were given a detailed post mortem examination. For each sample, all 72 tension members were pulled to break, and measurements were made of tensile strength, tensile modulus, and elongation at break. A typical set of these data, from an ITT cable sample, is given in Table VIII. The table also shows original values for the same tension members. (In 18 months of storage, no aging effect has been observed for control samples of any KEVLAR-49 tension members made by U.S. Polymeric.)

Note the decrease in mean strength and increase in coefficient of variation for the post-cabling 0.073"-diameter tension members. The members of this group show a definite bimodal distribution in strength, with strong peaks located near 150,000 and 250,000 psi. Apparently, the mechanism of strength degradation is highly selective--a phenomenon difficult to understand since the stresses of cabling were expected to be quite symmetric.

The post-cabling tension members showed relatively little decrease in tensile modulus or increase of coefficient of variation for this parameter. Note, however, that the coefficient of correlation of modulus to strength reversed sign during cabling for the 0.073" members. The reason for this reversal also is not understood.

Figures 10 and 11 show the distribution of strength and modulus values--before and after cabling, respectively--for the 0.073" members of the same ITT cable sample. Note the much greater spread in tensile strength for the post-cabling members.

Two characteristics of the KEVLAR-49 tension members were unaffected by cabling. The stress/strain curve remained quite linear and the members still showed no signs of an elastic limit. These factors suggested a rather simple-minded model that might be used to predict the true load at cable break and the mode in which it would break. Construction of the model begins with definition of relative member elongation at break as equalling the ratio of tensile strength to tensile modulus.

$$\frac{\text{Tensile Strength}}{\text{Tensile Modulus}} = \frac{S}{E} = \left(\frac{\Delta L}{L}\right)_c \quad (2)$$

The load carried by one helix of tension members is then approximately equal to the product of a geometry and construction constant K, the number of surviving members N, the average tensile modulus of these members \bar{E} , and the relative elongation of the members of the helix. Considering both helices and the total cable load:

$$\text{Cable Load} = \left[\frac{\Delta L}{L} \right] [K_1 \cdot N_1 \cdot \bar{E}_1 + k \cdot K_2 \cdot N_2 \cdot \bar{E}_2] \quad (3)$$

The factor k recognizes that the two helices may not stretch by the same amount. For the ITT and South Bay prototype cables, this factor was within 2% of unity. The model ignores compression of the cable core and changes of helix angles, and assumes that all cable cross sections will remain both planar and perpendicular to the cable axis. It allows rapid calculation of cable loads as a series of tension members begins to break, and requires only that the population of tension members and the average tensile modulus be adjusted each time a break occurs in a helix.

Table VIII and Figure 10 previously described the precabing properties of the tension members in the ITT prototype coaxial cable. Figure 12 applies Equation 3 to predict the cable strength that could be achieved if these properties were retained. For comparison, the figure also plots the cable strength that would result if all members had strength and modulus properties equal to their average values. The effects of strength and modulus variations are clear--an immediate loss of nearly 15,000 pounds in cable breaking strength.

Figure 13 plots the same calculation, but this time based on the post mortem properties of the ITT cable sample described by Table VIII and Figure 11. The maximum cable strength is reduced even more sharply, but many tension members must break before the cable can begin a general cascade of failure. The lower curve agrees closely, in mode and magnitude, with the observed behavior of the ITT prototype KEVLAR-49 coaxial cable.

The model described by Equation 3 is crude and temporary, but has given a much deeper insight into our understanding of the true behavior of KEVLAR-49 in multi-member cables. A much more accurate and sophisticated model, developed by Dr. Ronald Knapp at the Naval Undersea Center, is being programmed for computer operation. It will assign discrete strength and modulus values to each member, while allowing for core compressibility, torque and rotation effects, and intermember frictional stresses and stress transfer. The model, and examples of its application, will be described in a paper being prepared for the Marine Technology Society meeting in September, 1975. The new computerized model will allow rapid calculation and comparison of alternative designs.

Conclusions

Tension members built as a composite of KEVLAR-49 filaments in a resin matrix have many advantages over steel, including comparable or higher strength, much lower weight, and extremely long lifetimes under loaded flexure.

The material shows no evidence of flexure fatigue, as long as the filaments are captured in a helix which is shorter than the length increment affected by bending. Rather, the physical mechanism of failure is abrasion of the composite material against either the flexure substrate or other tension members. If this contact surface can be coated with a nonabrasive material, flexure lifetime is increased by at least a factor of 5.

The tension members are degraded by long-term exposure to sunlight and weather, or to a biologically rich seawater environment. In the former case, degradation results from ultraviolet irradiation of the filaments and erosion of the resin matrix. During ocean exposure, the resin is leached away and marine life (such as barnacles) may physically distort and penetrate the filament helix in forming an attachment to the member. No evidence has been encountered of attractiveness to or assault by fish during 20 months of exposure. For both exposures, a KEVLAR-49 tension member or cable should be adequately protected by a thin jacket of opaque polyurethane.

The tension members have a high coefficient of variation in tensile strength and tensile modulus, coupled with a completely linear stress/strain curve and nonyielding behavior at high stresses. These factors make the members difficult to analyze in cable systems. As a result, cable strength cannot be accurately predicted on the basis of average member properties. Design techniques are needed which treat the tension members individually, assigning specific values of strength and modulus to each member.

A still-unknown mechanism causes these tension members to degrade in tensile strength by as much as 50% during cabling. The most probable cause is asymmetric axial stresses caused by high and variable friction as the members pass through the cabling die and are crimped into a helix. This hypothesis is not yet proved. If true, this problem can be alleviated by reducing the angle of member convergence into the helix and by lubricating the die.

Use of KEVLAR-49 composite tension members can reduce armor weight in an electromechanical cable to the point that the electrical section represents about 80% of the cable weight in seawater. If further major reductions of in-water weight are to be made, they must be done through lightening of the electrical section. Table V demonstrates how this might be done, and shows that a 20-conductor cable can be built with a specific gravity less than 1.

Acknowledgements

The spirit of cooperation and communication which has prevailed among all companies supporting the effort described above is gratefully acknowledged. Specific thanks are due to DuPont, U.S. Polymeric, Philadelphia Resins, Air Logistics, ITT, Consolidated Products (South Bay) and Battelle Institute. The staffs of these companies have recognized the magnitude and future potential of a shared problem, and have willingly shared techniques, professional knowledge and (often proprietary) technical insight. We thank them.

The intuitive genius, craftsmanship and dedication of Mr. Herb Mummery, who operates the Hawaii Laboratory's materials test facility, are also appreciated. If it could be done, he would be awarded an earned PhD in Technical Competence.

References

1. KEVLAR-49 Data Manual, E.I. DuPont de Nemours & Company, Textile Fibers Department, Experimental Station, Wilmington, Delaware 19898.
2. Hofer, P.H. and Nalepa, H.J., "Composite Thermoplastic Glass Filament Reinforcement for Buoyant Submarine Cables RG-372 (XN-1)/U and RG-373(XN-1)/U," Union Carbide, (National Technical Information Services Document Number AD 828607), February 15, 1968.
3. U.S. Steel Specification Sheet for Coaxial, Double Armored, Electromechanical Cable 2J69RC, dated April, 1973.
4. Chiao, T.T. and Moore, R.L., "Tensile Properties of PRD-49 Fiber in Epoxy Matrix," Journal of Composite Materials, October, 1972.
5. Chiao, T.T. and Moore, R.L., "Organic Fiber/Epoxy Composites," Composites, January, 1973.
6. Berian, A.G., "An Impregnated High-Strength Organic Fiber for Oceanographic Strength Members," Proceedings of the Marine Technology Society, September, 1973, pp. 349-364.
7. Hightower, J.D., Wilkins, G.A., and Rosencrantz, D.M., "Development of PRD-49 Composite Tensile Strength Members," ASME Publication 73-WA/OCT-14, Winter Annual Meeting, Detroit, Michigan, October, 1973.

8. Swenson, R.C. and Stoltz, R.A., "Design and Construction of Cables for Sensor Systems," Sea Technology, October-November, 1973.
9. Kasper, R.G., "The Mechanical Response of an Electromechanical Array Cable Subject to Dynamic Forces," Proceedings of the Marine Technology Society, September, 1974, pp. 55-67.
10. U.S. Polymeric proprietary Formulation Number V-355.
11. Whitehill, A.S., Philadelphia Resins Corporation, personal communication.
12. Considine, R.J., Air Logistics Corporation, personal communication.
13. Scala, E., "High-Strength Filaments for Cables and Lines," Analysis of the Test Methods for High Modulus Fibers and Composites, ASTM STP 521, 1973, pp. 390-409.
14. Riewald, P.G., E.I. DuPont de Nemours & Company, personal communication.
15. Imperial Chemical Industries America, Inc., 151 South Street, Stamford, Connecticut 06904.
16. Uniroyal Chemical, Naugatuck, Connecticut 06770.
17. Formulations XP 4213.36 and XP 4213.37, Dow Chemical USA, Freeport, Texas 77541.
18. Bowers, W.E., "High Strength-to-Weight Cable for Deep Ocean Projects," Proceedings of the 22nd International Wire and Cable Symposium, December, 1973, pp. 279-285.
19. Gibson, P.T., White, F.G., Thomas, G.L., Cress, H.A., and Wilkins, G.A., "Evaluation of KEVLAR-Strengthened Electro-mechanical Cable," Proceedings of the Marine Technology Society, September, 1974, pp. 279-292.
20. "Final Report on Navy Contract N00123-73-C-1277," Battelle Institute, (National Technical Information Service Document Numbers AD 777688 and AD 777689), October, 1973.

Parameter	U.S. Polymeric (0.073"-O.D.)	Philadelphia Resins (PS-49-C.08)	Air Logistics (0.070"-O.D.)
<u>Number of Members Evaluated</u>	32	18	19
<u>Effective Member Diameter (in)</u>	0.073	0.088	0.070
<u>KEVLAR Cross-Sectional Fraction</u>	0.715	0.574	0.518
<u>Composite Tensile Modulus</u>			
Highest Value (psi)	12,920,000	11,210,000	10,260,000
Lowest Value (psi)	11,380,000	7,880,000	9,450,000
Mean Value (psi)	12,000,000	8,850,000	9,720,000
Standard Deviation (psi)	370,000	874,000	198,000
Coefficient of Variation	0.0308	0.0988	0.0204
<u>Composite Tensile Strength</u>			
Highest Value (psi)	277,200	192,400	249,500
Lowest Value (psi)	246,100	173,500	220,900
Mean Value (psi)	256,500	185,100	236,200
Standard Deviation (psi)	7,530	4,990	7,890
Coefficient of Variation	0.0294	0.0270	0.0334
<u>Mean Value, Filament T.M. (psi)</u>	16,790,000	15,200,000	18,760,000
<u>Mean Value, Filament T.S. (psi)</u>	358,900	317,800	455,800
<u>Product Moment Correlations</u>			
Of Modulus to Strength	+0.281	+0.114	+0.066
Of Ult. Elongation to Strength	+0.575	+0.163	+0.849
Of Ult. Elongation to Modulus	-0.623	-0.955	-0.471

Table III. Summary of Strength and Modulus Properties for
3 Types of KEVLAR-49 Tension Members.

Load As % of Ultimate Stress	Flexure Cycles to First Failure					
	U.S. Polymeric 0.073"-OD	18 Yarns Twisted 1420-Denier KEVLAR-49	Philadelphia Resins PS-49-C.08	Air Logistics		Steel 225,000 psi
				KEVLAR-49	S-Glass	
20%	>2,000,000*	238,830	No data	1993 3030	411,696	1039 1092 1017
30%	121,614	No data	>634,000*	468 809	59,979	No data
40%	5,658 10,026 76,761 3,940 48,010	No data	13,914	< 1	19,275	No data
50%	18,001 8,646	No data	115 800 1,630	< 1	1,889 3,314	No data
*Member not broken after this many flexure cycles.						

Table IV. Results of flexure tests under axial load

Specimen Number	Manufacturer	Cable Load at Failure of First Tension Member (lb)	Maximum Cable Load (lb)
U-4	South Bay	40,000	52,700
J-9*	South Bay	40,400	45,900
J-10	South Bay	40,000	48,700
J-11*	South Bay	-----	46,800
J-12	South Bay	45,000	50,800
J-14	South Bay	40,000	53,500
J-15#	South Bay	-----	47,200
J-16	South Bay	37,800	51,200
T-9 [@]	ITT	34,200	44,200
S-2	ITT	46,500	55,500
S-3	ITT	45,400	51,600

*Previously subjected to 100,000 $\pm 14^\circ$ flexure cycles at cable load of 10,000 pounds.
#Pulled from socket in early test.
[@]Many kinked members

Table VI. Results of pull-to-break tests of prototype KEVLAR-49 coaxial cables.

Parameter	0.073"-Diameter Members		0.097"-Diameter Members	
	Before Cabling	Post Mortem	Before Cabling	Post Mortem
<u>Number of Members Evaluated</u>	44	44	28	28
<u>Composite Tensile Modulus</u>				
Highest Value (psi)	13,100,000	13,200,000	12,300,000	11,800,000
Lowest Value (psi)	11,900,000	11,000,000	11,000,000	9,950,000
Mean Value (psi)	12,600,000	11,800,000	11,700,000	10,700,000
Standard Deviation (psi)	316,000	405,000	311,000	430,000
Coefficient of Variation	0.025	0.034	0.027	0.040
<u>Composite Tensile Strength</u>				
Highest Value (psi)	294,000	269,000	264,000	217,000
Lowest Value (psi)	228,000	146,000	221,000	140,000
Mean Value (psi)	264,000	217,000	249,000	194,000
Standard Deviation (psi)	16,700	40,800	11,300	14,700
Coefficient of Variation	0.063	0.188	0.045	0.076
<u>Product Moment Correlation of Modulus to Strength</u>	+0.215	-0.282	+0.131	+0.230

Table VIII. Summary of strength and modulus properties for KEVLAR-49 tension members, before and after assembly into the ITT prototype KEVLAR-49 coaxial cable.

1. Variation of strength-to-weight ratio with ocean depth for several cables and tension members.

2. Typical stress/strain curves for steel and 3 composite KEVLAR-49 tension members.

3. Typical elongation under load for 2 KEVLAR-49 tension members.

4. Fixture used for tests of flexure under load.

5. KEVLAR-49 composite tension members after 20 months of exposure; seawater (top), control sample (middle) and weather (bottom).

6. Prototype array cable.

- KEVLAR-49 Load-Bearing Core
- 17,000-pound Breaking Strength
- 20 Conductors, as 10 twisted pairs
- Specific Gravity < 1.02
- All Voids Filled
- Torque Balanced

7. Cross section of final array cable design.

8. Prototype KEVLAR-49 coaxial cable from South Bay.

9. Epoxy block from socket used to terminate KEVLAR-49 coaxial cable; side view (left) and end view.

10. Scatter plot of tensile strength and tensile modulus, as originally measured at U.S. Polymeric, for 0.073"-diameter KEVLAR-49 tension members used in the ITT prototype coaxial cable. The star represents average values.

11. Strength/modulus scatter plot for the same tension members shown in Figure 10, measured after removal from the ITT cable. The star represents average values.

12. Computed strength of ITT prototype coaxial cable using "as-built" properties of tension members; (a) assuming all members have strength and modulus equal to their averages, and (b) allowing each member to have its own properties.

13. Computed strength of ITT prototype coaxial cable using post-cabling properties of tension members; (a) assuming all members have strength and modulus equal to their averages, and (b) allowing each member to have its own properties.